

Supplementary Table – PubMed Search Strategy

Database: PubMed

Search date: April 2025

Search nº	Search strategies	Studies identified
1#	"aortic aneurysm"[MeSH Terms] OR ("aortic"[All Fields] AND "aneurysm"[All Fields]) OR "aortic aneurysm"[All Fields] OR ("aortic aneurysm"[MeSH Terms] OR ("aortic"[All Fields] AND "aneurysm"[All Fields]) OR "aortic aneurysm"[All Fields]) OR ("aortic"[All Fields] AND "aneurysms"[All Fields]) OR "aortic aneurysms"[All Fields].	19.595
2#	"aged"[MeSH Terms] OR "aged"[All Fields] OR "aged"[MeSH Terms] OR "aged"[All Fields] OR "elderly"[All Fields] OR "elderlies"[All Fields] OR "elderly s"[All Fields] OR "elderlys"[All Fields].	1.289.632
3#	"hospital s"[All Fields] OR "hospitalisation"[All Fields] OR "hospitalization"[MeSH Terms] OR "hospitalization"[All Fields] OR "hospitalised"[All Fields] OR "hospitalising"[All Fields] OR "hospitality"[All Fields] OR "hospitalisations"[All Fields] OR "hospitalizations"[All Fields] OR "hospitalize"[All Fields] OR "hospitalized"[All Fields] OR "hospitalizing"[All Fields] OR "hospitals"[MeSH Terms] OR "hospitals"[All Fields] OR "hospital"[All Fields] OR "hospital s"[All Fields] OR "hospitalisation"[All Fields] OR "hospitalization"[MeSH Terms] OR "hospitalization"[All Fields] OR "hospitalised"[All Fields] OR "hospitalising"[All Fields] OR "hospitality"[All Fields] OR "hospitalisations"[All Fields] OR "hospitalizations"[All Fields] OR "hospitalize"[All Fields] OR "hospitalized"[All Fields] OR "hospitalizing"[All Fields] OR "hospitals"[MeSH Terms] OR "hospitals"[All Fields] OR "hospital"[All Fields].	3.299.188
4#	1# AND 2# AND 3#	4.773
Language: Portuguese, Spanish and English		

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